

Antibody Characterization Report for Fc receptor gamma-chain (*FCER1G*)

YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

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Target:

Protein name used in this report: Fc receptor gamma-chain

Recommended protein name: High affinity immunoglobulin epsilon receptor subunit gamma

Alternative protein names: Fc-epsilon RI-gamma, IgE Fc receptor subunit gamma (FceRI gamma)

Gene name: *FCER1G*

Uniprot: P30273

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science [1]. In this study, we characterized seven Fc receptor gamma-chain commercial antibodies for western blot and immunoprecipitation using a standardized experimental protocol [2] based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. We identified many well-performing antibodies and encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibody for their specific needs. A THP-1 *FCER1G* KO line was custom made at Abcam and was used in this study. THP-1 was selected based on evidence of appropriate Fc receptor gamma-chain protein expression determined through DepMap [3, 4]. We were unable to characterize the antibodies by immunofluorescence, as the KO cell line showed significant cell death.

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
ATCC	TIB-202	CVCL_0006	THP-1	WT
Abcam	ab288699	CVCL_D5HB	THP-1	<i>FCER1G</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the Fc receptor gamma-chain antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$)	Vendors recommended applications
Abclonal	A12889	60020101	AB_2759732	polyclonal	-	rabbit	2.56	Wb
Cell Signaling Technology	20379	1	AB_3094923	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.04	Wb
Cell Signaling Technology	78401**	1	AB_3094924	recombinant-mono	E6Y1A	rabbit	0.12	Wb,IP,IF
GeneTex	GTX108487	44496	AB_1950266	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.73	Wb,IF
GeneTex	GTX636884**	44683	AB_2943646	recombinant-mono	HL1418	rabbit	1.00	Wb,IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-28832	XC3524112A	AB_2546308	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.73	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-115222	XB3491400	AB_2899858	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb,IF

Wb=western blot, IP= immunoprecipitation, IF=immunofluorescence, **=recombinant antibody, NA=not available

Materials and methods

Antibodies

All the Fc receptor gamma-chain antibodies tested are listed in Table 2. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit is from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 65-6120). Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-rabbit secondary antibodies is from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A21429).

Cell culture

Cells were cultured in RPMI 1640 (ATCC modification) (Gibco, cat. number A1049101) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 2 mM L-glutamine (Wisent cat. number 609-065, 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent cat. number 450201) and 0.05 mM of 2-Mercaptoethanol (Gibco, cat. number 21985-023).

THP-1 WT and *FCER1G* KO (listed in Table 1) were treated with 200 ng/ml of phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) (Abcam, cat. number ab147465) for 2 days. 200 ng/ml of PMA was added to fresh medium in both day 1 and day 2 [5].

Antibody screening by western blot

Western blots were performed as described in our standard operating procedure [6]. THP-1 WT and *FCER1G* KO treated or not with PMA were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder from GeneDireX (cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WG1201BOX) ran with MES SDS buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP000202), loaded in LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0008) with 1x sample reducing agent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0009) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) from Cell Signaling (cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary

antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Immunoprecipitation was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [7]. Antibody-beads conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg or 20 µl of antibody 20379 to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with with 30µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 hr at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

PMA-treated THP-1 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C. 0.75 ml aliquots at 0.8 mg/ml (0.6 mg) of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 hr at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP lysis buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels. VeriBlot for IP Detection Reagent:HRP (Abcam, cat. number ab131366) was used as a secondary detection system at a concentration of 0.1 µg/ml.

Figure 1: Fc receptor gamma-chain antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: Fc receptor gamma-chain antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 1: Fc receptor gamma-chain antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of THP-1 WT and *FCER1G* KO were prepared, and 40 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated Fc receptor gamma-chain antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. Antibody dilution used: A12889 at 1/500, 20379 at 1/500, 78401** at 1/500, GTX108487 at 1/500, GTX636884** at 1/200, PA5-28832 at 1/500, PA5-115222 at 1/500. Predicted band size: 9.7 kDa. **=recombinant antibody

Figure 2: Fc receptor gamma-chain antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

THP-1 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 2.0 µg of the indicated Fc receptor gamma-chain antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the indicated Fc receptor gamma-chain antibody. For western blot, 78401** was used at 1/1000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=6% starting material; UB=6% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. **=recombinant antibody

References

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